

1 **OPTIMIZATION-BASED HIGHWAY TRAFFIC STATE ESTIMATION WITH BOUND**
2 **GUARANTEES**

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1 INTRODUCTION

Traffic state estimation (TSE) is key in transportation systems enabling a wealth of applications related to traffic monitoring and control, Timotheou et al. (1). Nonetheless, estimating the traffic state of a transportation system is a challenging task due to the system scale, the scarcity of spatio-temporal measurements, the low-quality of the collected data and the modelling uncertainty emanating from the unpredictable nature of human driving behaviour.

For these reasons, TSE has attracted a lot of attention leading to the development of numerous methods, both model-based and data-driven, Seo et al. (2). Despite the large body of literature on TSE, most research works estimate point values for states, i.e., no information is provided with regards to the upper and lower bounds of the true states. This, however, may lead to significant performance degradation. For example, in the context of the Asymmetric Cell Transmission Model (ACTM), implicit mode switching methods have been developed that alternate between cell modes (free-flow, congestion) and apply linear Kalman filtering in the resulting system, Muñoz et al. (3). Nonetheless, interpretation of some state modes is erroneous because estimated values are near the boundary of alternative modes, leading to large deviations from the true state.

Guaranteed bounds on the state variables are provided in Kurzhanskiy and Varaiya (4). Here, the authors develop an ACTM-based estimator and predictor that provides bounds on the current and future states that are guaranteed to contain the true state. Although the approach is systematic and simple, it may lead to conservative bounds due to the local nature of exploited information and the consideration of state bounds from only the previous time step.

Our work aims to develop approaches that achieve TSE with tight bound guarantees. Towards this direction, we introduce a moving horizon methodology that exploits information from the entire network and considers several past time-steps to tighten state bounds. The methodology is applied for highway traffic density estimation with bound guarantees using the ACTM. In this context, the main contribution of this work is the development of three novel algorithms with a different trade-off between bounding performance and computational complexity.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

We consider the class of discrete nonlinear uncertain systems described by:

$$\mathbf{x}_{t+1} = \boldsymbol{\gamma}_t(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t) + \boldsymbol{\eta}_t, \quad t \in \mathbb{N} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_x}$ is the state vector, $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_u}$ is the input vector, $\boldsymbol{\gamma}_t : \mathbb{R}^{N_x} \times \mathbb{R}^{N_u} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{N_x}$ denotes the nonlinear function of the system dynamics at time t , and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{N_x}$ represents additive model noise.

The nonlinear system (1) is monitored by a set of sensors $\mathcal{R} = \{1, \dots, N_s\}$, $N_s \leq N_x$, monitoring a subset of states, and characterized by the compact output vector $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_s}$; i.e.,

$$\mathcal{R} : \mathbf{y}_t = \mathbf{H}_t \mathbf{x}_t + \boldsymbol{\omega}_t, \quad t \in \mathbb{N} \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\omega}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{N_s}$ is the measurement noise. We assume that the model noise of each state i , $\eta_{i,t}$, $i \in \mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, N_x\}$, $t \in \mathbb{N}$, and the measurement noise $\omega_{j,t}$ of sensor $j \in \mathcal{R}$, $t \in \mathbb{N}$ are uniformly bounded; i.e., $\eta_i^l \leq \eta_{i,t} \leq \eta_i^u$, and $\omega_j^l \leq \omega_{j,t} \leq \omega_j^u$. The lower and upper bounds of the model and measurement noise η_i^l , η_i^u , and ω_j^l , ω_j^u , are a priori known for all $i \in \mathcal{N}$ and $j \in \mathcal{R}$. It is also assumed that the initial state has known bounds, i.e. $x_{i,0}^l \leq x_{i,0} \leq x_{i,0}^u$, $i \in \mathcal{N}$.

TSE with bounds guarantees aims to find the best lower and upper bounds for each state, \mathbf{x}_K^l and \mathbf{x}_K^u , given the set of the first K observations $\mathbf{Y}_1^K = [\mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_K]$ and input vectors $\mathbf{U}_0^{K-1} = [\mathbf{u}_0, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{K-1}]$.

1 3. GENERAL SOLUTION METHODOLOGY

2 The optimal solution to this problem can be obtained by solving $2N_x$ optimization problems; N_x
 3 minimization problems to obtain the lower bounds on variables $x_{i,K}$, denoted by $x_{i,K}^l$, and N_x max-
 4 imization problems to obtain the upper bounds $x_{i,K}^u$. To achieve the best possible bounds on the
 5 states that guarantee the inclusion of the true state, one needs to consider the entire collection of
 6 observation and input vectors, and also allow the model and measurement noise to vary freely
 7 within specified limits. The best lower bound on $x_{i,K}$ is obtained by solving the problem

$$\text{minimize}_{\{\mathbf{x}_t, t \in \mathbb{N}_0^K, \boldsymbol{\eta}_t, t \in \mathbb{N}_0^{K-1}, \boldsymbol{\omega}_t, t \in \mathbb{N}_1^K\}} x_{i,K} \quad (3a)$$

$$x_{i,t+1} = \gamma_{i,t}(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t) + \eta_{i,t}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}, t \in \mathbb{N}_0^{K-1}, \quad (3b)$$

$$y_{j,t} = \mathbf{h}_{j,t} \mathbf{x}_t + \omega_{j,t}, \quad j \in \mathcal{R}, t \in \mathbb{N}_1^K, \quad (3c)$$

$$\eta_i^l \leq \eta_{i,t} \leq \eta_i^u, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}, t \in \mathbb{N}_0^{K-1}, \quad (3d)$$

$$\omega_j^l \leq \omega_{j,t} \leq \omega_j^u, \quad j \in \mathcal{R}, t \in \mathbb{N}_1^K, \quad (3e)$$

$$x_{i,0}^l \leq x_{i,0} \leq x_{i,0}^u, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (3f)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_t \in \mathcal{X}_t, \quad t \in \mathbb{N}_0^K, \quad (3g)$$

8 while the best upper bound on $x_{i,K}$ by solving the corresponding maximization problem

$$\text{maximize}_{\{\mathbf{x}_t, t \in \mathbb{N}_0^K, \boldsymbol{\eta}_t, t \in \mathbb{N}_0^{K-1}, \boldsymbol{\omega}_t, t \in \mathbb{N}_1^K\}} x_{i,K} \quad (4)$$

subject to constraints (3b)-(3g).

9 In formulation (3), set \mathbb{N}_a^b denotes the set of physical numbers between a and b , i.e., $\mathbb{N}_a^b =$
 10 $\{a, a+1, \dots, b\}$, \mathcal{X}_t denotes a general set that includes any physical or logical constraints on the
 11 system states, while $\mathbf{h}_{j,t} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times N_x}$ denotes the j -th row of matrix \mathbf{H}_t .

12 The optimal solution of (3) and (4) is very challenging for two main reasons. First, the
 13 computational complexity of the problem grows significantly with increasing time, as the approach
 14 requires consideration of the entire collection of observation and input vectors. Second, the nonlin-
 15 earity of function $\gamma_{i,t}(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t)$ in (3b) makes the problem nonconvex, while its form may even prohibit
 16 the transformation of (3b) into a standard form for global optimization. The same challenge arises
 17 when \mathcal{X}_t is a non-convex set.

18 To deal with the growing computational complexity of increasing K , a moving horizon
 19 optimization approach is proposed in this work that solves (3) and (4) by considering only the
 20 latest H observation and input vectors, i.e., \mathbf{Y}_{K-H+1}^K and \mathbf{U}_{K-H}^{K-1} . In this case, the bounds on the
 21 initial state values, \mathbf{x}_{K-H} , are set equal to the bounds obtained when solving the problem during
 22 the $K-H$ th time step. In this way, the lower/upper bounding problem for the i -th state at time
 23 K has the same formulation but replaces \mathbb{N}_a^b with \mathbb{N}_{a+K-H}^b . Although approximate, this approach
 24 guarantees to find an outer approximation of the optimal solution which tightens for increasing H .

Dealing with the second challenge, requires the consideration of the nature of $\gamma_{i,t}(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t)$ in
 the considered context. In this work we examine the problem in the context of ACTM. We show
 that the inflow and outflow functions of ACTM can be expressed as the difference of two nonlinear
 functions of the form

$$\max\{0, \min\{a_1 x_{1,t} + b_1, a_2 x_{2,t} + b_2, b_3\}\}, \quad (5)$$

25 and propose four solution algorithms for its solution:

- 26 1. **MILP** accurately models all ACTM terms of the form (5) using Mixed Integer Linear
 27 Programming (MILP) constraints.

FIGURE 1 Highway network considered for performance evaluation.

- 1 2. **MILPrelax**, relaxes the integer variables of MILP algorithm to produce a Linear Pro-
- 2 gramming formulation.
- 3 3. **ConvHull** derives the convex hull of the model's nonlinear functions (5), also yielding
- 4 a Linear Programming formulation.
- 5 4. **Heuristic** is a low-complexity algorithm that finds density bounds for each cell by only
- 6 considering currently available density bounds on neighbouring cells, in the same spirit
- 7 with Kurzhanskiy and Varaiya (4).

8 4. FINDINGS

9 To evaluate the performance of the proposed algorithms we consider a 3-lane highway stretch
 10 of 10 cells with lengths $L_i = \{0.5, 0.6, 0.5, 0.5, 0.75, 0.6, 0.5, 0.5, 0.8, 0.75\}$ km, as shown in Fig. 1.
 11 We consider the following ACTM parameter values: $u^f = 100$ km/h, $T_s = 10$ s, $w = 25$ km/h,
 12 $Q^M = 6000$ veh/h, $\rho^J = 300$ veh/km, and $H = 5$. For the process and measurement noise we as-
 13 sume that $-4 \leq \eta_t \leq 4$ and $-10 \leq \omega_t \leq 10$. For simulation purposes we consider a 3-hour morning
 14 peak-hour scenario where the main input flow increases from 500 veh/h to 9000 veh/h in one hour,
 15 remains constant for one hour, decreases to 3500 veh/h in half an hour, and remains constant after-
 16 wards. On-ramp input flows follow a similar pattern with ranges [300, 2000] veh/hour and [500,
 17 3000] veh/hour for the first and second on-ramps, respectively.

18 Fig. 2 depicts the derived density bounds of four specific cells over time using the different
 19 algorithms: cells 2, 4 and 6 whose density is unmeasurable, and cell 7 whose state is measurable.
 20 From the figure it is evident that the measurable states have significantly better performance, while
 21 all algorithms perform equally well. In contrast, the unmeasurable states yield significantly worse
 22 performance especially for time periods that the cell is in a congested state, while the performance
 23 of the developed algorithms varies significantly. It can be observed that the performance of the
 24 ConvHull and MILP algorithms is very similar. The performance of the Heuristic algorithm is also
 25 very good especially for time periods of low density variability; during periods of high variability
 26 (e.g. see the lower bound density of Fig. 2(a) during period [1.1, 2.3]h) the performance of the
 27 Heuristic algorithm worsens because it does not exploit a moving horizon approach to restrict
 28 state values based on previous measurements. Contrary to these algorithms, the performance of
 29 MILPrelax is very poor.

30 5. CONCLUSIONS

31 This work has examined the problem of traffic state estimation with bound guarantees, introduced
 32 a moving horizon optimization-based methodology for its solution and developed four algorithms
 33 with different solution quality and execution speed trade-off. The results highlight the importance
 34 of tight function approximations using convex polytopes and the consideration of moving-horizon,
 35 network-wide algorithms to obtain high-quality solutions, especially under high uncertainty.

FIGURE 2 Traffic density bounds obtained from different algorithms of cells: (a) 2, (b) 4, (c) 6, and (d) 7.

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